

EDUCATIONAL STRATEGY TO COMBAT THE USE OF ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES BY ADOLESCENTS

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Liliane Rodrigues de Araujo

Graduated in Pedagogy. Master in Education. Email: liliaraujoe10@hotmail.com.

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

*Pedagogue. Philosopher. Sociologist. Scientific Consultant. Email:
sergiorodrigues52@hotmail.com.*

Vinícius da Silva Santos

Biologist. Master in Education and Technologies. Email: viniciusbiologo33@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The work addresses the use of alcoholic beverages by adolescents. It is justified by the fact that the consumption of alcohol by adolescents increases every day. Its scientific relevance is characterized by the fact that this subject is little studied by the academy. This is a bibliographical research. It aims to enable the understanding of the possible causes that lead adolescents to consume alcoholic beverages. Any beverage with an alcoholic strength greater than 0.5 GL is considered an alcoholic beverage (Bill No. 2733/2008). Alcohol has been consumed for a long time. However, before the distillation process, the drinks had a lower alcohol content as they underwent fermentation. In Brazil, there are laws that prohibit the sale of alcoholic beverages to minors, however, there is no rigid control. Confirmation that the legislation is not being complied with is portrayed in the fact that 39.22% of adolescents under 18 years of age reported that they buy their own alcoholic beverages, not finding any difficulty in obtaining them. The conclusions are that there is a need for clarification by education professionals in order to keep adolescents away from alcohol consumption. Excessive alcohol use can disrupt the growth of normal brain cells, which can interfere with teens' performance in school and sports. There is also the feeling of overcoming obstacles placed by society as barriers that the teenager is forced to overcome and who, without being able to count on the support of family members, rely on alcohol and the results are the sad fatalities that are commonly witnessed.

Keywords: alcoholic beverages; teenagers; Use of alcoholic beverages by adolescents.

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of alcoholic beverages, especially by adolescents, has become a public policy problem, because due to excesses, the number of car accidents increases and, in particular, these fall, firsthand, in the government dependencies of the SUS, the which exceeds the costs of the state machine.

Allied to this are cultural, sociological, philosophical, epistemological and existential questions that, arising from scientific advances, have clarified points about what was previously ignored, due to lack of deeper studies. Varella (2013) says that for this turnaround in relation to alcohol use among adolescents, which occurred abruptly from one generation to another, several risk factors competed. The first is that the consumption of alcoholic beverages is accepted and even encouraged by society. Parents who panic when they discover their son or daughter has smoked marijuana or taken an *ecstasy pill*; however, at a party, they think it's normal for them to drink because, after all, everyone drinks.

But, when considered in terms of volume, alcoholic beverages cause more damage to health, directly and indirectly, than drugs considered illicit. This study aims to clarify some points about the issue of alcohol consumption by adolescents, as well as to break some *taboos*, which are not justified in the academic environment, such as, alcohol consumption is one thing, alcoholism is another, the first can lead to the second, while the second is characterized as a disease that needs serious and rigorous treatment, and, if we consider that both can lead to death, the causes are extremely divergent.

There is an urgent need for efficient and effective control over the marketing of alcoholic beverages to adolescents, and these measures must start with the families themselves. Professionals linked to the fields of education, health and supervisory bodies are responsible for clarifying and supporting parents and their children.

CONCEPTS OF ADOLESCENCE

Adolescence is configured as the transition period between childhood and adulthood, this phase of life is constituted as a period of transformations, whether physical, psychic and, mainly, social in the life of an adolescent. According to some authors, adolescence lasts approximately from 12 (twelve) or 13 (thirteen) years to the beginning of 20 (twenty) years. So there is no clear definition for its starting or ending point. Generally, adolescence begins at

puberty, that is, through the process that leads to sexual maturity. Thus, puberty is considered the period in which menarche (1st menstruation) occurs in girls and the 1st ejaculation in boys, thus, it is understood that there is already the ability to reproduce.

Adolescence is a period of changes, whether physical or psychological, accompanied by changes in emotions, biological changes and all these changes are explained through interaction with the environment in which they live (SOUZA, 2012).

Talking about adolescence implies, in a way, a reference to the biological. But it seems to us that in the current experience, it refers, above all, to the field of the senses of this contemporary experience, in a way of subjectivating itself. Adolescence is perceived as a crucial scene in the construction of personal and societal narratives. Adolescence is naturalized as an essential period for the growth of the individual and for the development of society insofar as young people are centers of change.

Adolescence continues, as a phase of human existence, shrouded in myths, taboos, concepts and preconceptions, a time of changes, discoveries and challenges; for this, the teenager should not face the adult world as a destroyer of interpersonal values, but as a new culture that has something of relevance to be added to his already conceived inner superego. (SOUZA, 2012, p. 09).

This phase of life “is considered crucial in the development of the individual, as it marks the structuring of the personality” (OSÓRIO, 1989, p. 32). It is also configured as a stage of immaturity in search of maturity. That is, not only is it a moment of the individual's bodily development, but it is also marked by cognitive changes that, according to the author, influence the development of the adolescent's personality.

Adolescence is the period from puberty (approximately 12-13 years old) to reaching full adulthood. According to Stanley Hall, adolescence ends comparatively late, between 22 and 25 years of age. (...) In terms of the theory of recapitulation, adolescence corresponds to the time when the human race was going through a period of turbulence and transition. Hall described adolescence as a rebirth, so that higher, fully human characteristics can be born (OSÓRIO, 1989).

ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGE CONCEPT

An alcoholic beverage is considered to be any beverage with an alcohol content greater than 0.5 GL (Bill No. 2733/2008). Alcohol has been consumed for a long time . However, before the distillation process, the drinks had a lower alcohol content as they underwent

fermentation. They were beer and wine. Alcohol is a psychotropic drink. In addition to causing addiction, it also causes changes in behavior. It begins with a change in mood accompanied by euphoria, then comes the moment of drowsiness, where the individual no longer has his motor coordination and presents depressive behavior. This happens due to the fact that alcohol acts directly on the central nervous system (ARAÚJO, 2013).

Law no. 8,918, of July 14, 1994, authorizes the creation of the Intersectoral Commission for Beverages and other measures, states in its article 1 that the obligation to standardize the production and inspection of the beverage trade, as in verbis :

Art. 1 It is established, throughout the national territory, the mandatory registration, standardization, classification, inspection and supervision of the production and trade of beverages.

[...]

Art. 11. The Executive Power shall establish in regulation, in addition to other measures, the specific provisions referring to the classification, standardization, labeling, analysis of products, raw materials, inspection and inspection of equipment, installations and hygienic-sanitary conditions of industrial, craft and homemade products, as well as the inspection of production and the supervision of trade referred to in this law (*Ibid* .)

Decree No. 3,510, of June 16, 2000 amends provisions of the Regulation approved by Decree No. 2,314, of September 4, 1997, which provides for the standardization, classification, registration, inspection, production and inspection of beverages .

“[...] Art. 10. Beverages will be classified as non-alcoholic and alcoholic beverages.

§ 1 A non-alcoholic beverage is a beverage with an alcoholic strength of up to half a percent by volume, at twenty degrees Celsius. (Included by Decree No. 3,510 of 2000).

§ 2 An alcoholic beverage is a beverage with an alcoholic strength above half and up to fifty-four percent by volume, at twenty degrees Celsius. (Included by Decree No. 3,510 of 2000)

§ 3 For the purpose of this Regulation, the alcoholic strength of a drink will be expressed in percentage of ethyl alcohol volume, at a temperature of twenty degrees Celsius.”

Law no. 9294, of July 15, 1996 (DOU 07/16/1996) which provides for restrictions on the use and advertising of tobacco products, alcoholic beverages, medicines, therapies and agricultural pesticides, under the terms of §4 of art. 220 of the Federal Constitution, amended by Law No. 10167, of December 27, 2000, states that, “**Sole Paragraph.** For the purposes of this Law, alcoholic beverages are considered to be drinkable beverages with an alcoholic strength greater than thirteen degrees Gay Lussac (GL).”

Bill No. 2,733/2008, assessed under a constitutional urgency regime, conceptualizes alcoholic beverages as those with a graduation equal to or greater than 0.5° GL (and no longer those containing from 13° GL), thus expanding the list of the respective ²products to be its restricted advertising, which includes beers, wines, *ices* and other beverages belonging to the same group.

The Regional Legislative Decree n° 14/2008/A of 11-06-2008, in its article 2.º - provides the definition of alcoholic beverage, with the following wording:

“For the purposes of this diploma, an alcoholic beverage is considered to be any beverage that, by fermentation, distillation or addition, contains an alcoholic strength greater than 0.5% volume” (DIÁRIO DA REPÚBLICA n° 111; series I of 06/11/ 2008).

LEGAL ASPECTS ON THE CONSUMPTION OF ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES BY ADOLESCENTS

According to Varella (2013) alcohol is toxic at any dose; and Laranjeira (2013) reinforces the doctor's statement by saying that it is toxic at any dose; the difference is only in the intensity of the toxic effects. Lower doses are less toxic than higher ones, which does not mean that, consumed in small amounts, alcohol ceases to bring biological damage to pregnant women and teenagers, for example. It does, although advertising is responsible for making people forget about the toxic component of alcohol, especially during growth, when not only the body, but also the brain develops at an amazing speed. In Brazil, most teenagers still don't drink, but those who do, drink a lot and with consumption peaks. Although little is said, this consumption pattern - the person does not drink anything during the week, but on the weekend drinks five vodkas or ten beers -, from a biological point of view, is very harmful for the organism.

In Brazil, there are laws that prohibit the sale of alcoholic beverages to minors, however, there is no rigid control. In the center of São Paulo, very close to a large school, in front of which there is a supermarket, often in the morning, you can see a group of high school students,

²INDICATION OF ALCOHOLIC CONTENT IN GL (GAY-LUSSAC). www.sbirt.ibict.br

Joseane Machado de Oliveira - SENAI – RS – June 8, 2006

Alcohol content can be expressed in terms of:

- °Gay Lussac (°GL= %volume/volume): amount in milliliters of absolute alcohol contained in 100 milliliters of hydro-alcoholic mixture. The °GL directly gives the percentage of alcohol in the mixture by volume. Therefore, the alcohol content of 30°GL is equivalent to 30% of alcohol in the mixture. However, as the volume of oil derivatives varies according to temperature, the result obtained is unrealistic, that is, the value read takes into account the expansion of molecules, due to this, the INPM (National Institute of Weights and Measures) created the so-called INPM grade which gives the percentage by weight of the product.

therefore between 14 and 17 years old, having a beer at the supermarket door . It is obvious that they managed to buy beer despite their young age (VARELLA, 2013).

According to Laranjeira (2013), a survey carried out in Diadema and Paulínia, two cities in the state of São Paulo, showed that adolescent interviewers were able to buy alcoholic beverages in 95% of the establishments visited (worldwide, the acceptable rate is 10%), which denotes total lack of control of the situation. And he complements by saying that we live in an uncontrolled market, strategically favored by the alcohol industry. In Brazil, there are a million points of sale of alcohol, one for every 180,000 inhabitants, the advertising is quite intense, the price is low and the lack of control over the sale of alcohol to minors prevails (Id .) .

Decree-Law no. 3,688, of October 3, 1941, which deals with the Law of Criminal Misdemeanors, states in its article 63 that serving alcoholic beverages to persons under eighteen years of age constitutes a crime, subject to imprisonment.

Law no. 8069, of July 13, 1990 (Statute of the Child and Adolescent) states that,

[...] Art. 243. Sell, supply even if free of charge, administer or deliver, in any way, to the child or adolescent, without just cause, products whose components may cause physical or psychological dependence, even if for improper use, the penalty is detention of 2 (two) to 4 (four) years, and a fine, if the fact does not constitute a more serious crime (Wording provided by Law No. 10,764, of 11.12.2003).

Confirmation that the legislation is not being complied with is portrayed in the fact that 39.22% of adolescents under 18 years of age reported that they buy their own alcoholic beverages, not finding any difficulty in obtaining them. Although there is a legal ban on the consumption of alcohol for minors under 18 (eighteen) years of age, alcohol is a drug legalized by Brazilian society and its social consumption is accepted, as the use of alcohol among adolescents is naturally common in social environments, especially in parties with friends. In these cases, many adolescents drink frequently and find it difficult to refuse to drink, mainly because alcohol acts as a facilitator of acceptance by the group of friends. Adolescents also consume alcoholic beverages in the family environment, at festivities, or even in public environments, demonstrating the need to create mechanisms or skills so that the adolescent will resist this social pressure from family, friends and the media, considered factors determinants for the consumption of alcoholic beverages (LLAMBRICH, 2005; OSTERBERG, 2004; GALLEGO *et al.* , 2005; PECHANSKY *et al.* , 2004).

CAUSES OF ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION BY ADOLESCENTS

Adolescence is marked by great vulnerability, uncertainty, suffering from limitations imposed by adults and even more by the need to guarantee oneself in a world that does not understand or accept it. From these confrontations, affirmation needs are born, which are combined with rites of passage, true challenges that lead them to face/face extreme situations, including the exaggerated consumption of alcoholic beverages, which become worrying behaviors if they remain into adulthood .

Without neglecting the genetic and emotional factors that influence drink consumption – alcohol reduces the level of anxiety and some people are more prone to developing alcoholism –, peer pressure, the feeling of omnipotence typical of youth, low cost of the drink, the lack of control in the supply and consumption of products containing alcohol, the absence of social limits contribute to the fact that the first contact with the drink occurs earlier and earlier (VARELLA, 2013).

Adolescence is the group that generates the greatest concern regarding alcohol consumption, as the habit of drinking is progressively increasing among young people and there is no effective control by public health agencies to regulate and curb this practice. Government entities have not developed specific and regular programs in schools and in the media in order to prevent the population from the various harmful effects of alcohol (VARELLA, 2013).

The exaggerated consumption of alcoholic beverages ends up deceiving young people, giving the impression that it can help them overcome difficulties in social life. However, it increases the chance of the young person opting for some risky behavior, reducing the possibility of safe sex or getting involved in car accidents. In addition to these risks, it is known that the earlier a young person starts drinking, the greater the chance of becoming an alcoholic adult (VARELLA, 2013).

According to research carried out by NIDA (National Institute of Drug Abuse), one in every 20 young people, between 15 and 17 years old, drink alcoholic beverages and 37% of young people interviewed had taken five or more drinks, at least two weeks preceded the research.

In addition to the symptoms of drunkenness, excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages is one of the main causes of traffic accidents, as alcohol causes motor incoordination and delay of reflexes; however, the most important factor as a cause of traffic accidents is the issue of loss of self-criticism, since, under the action of alcohol, people feel more courageous,

dare more, think less about the risks and consequences of their actions. acts (MANSUR, 1988; JERNIGAN, 2001; OSTERBERG, 2004).

Allied to all the statements of the aforementioned authors, the intoxicating factor of alcohol consumption by adolescents is the reduction and even elimination of shyness, which, if not handled properly, leads to exaggerated and violent behavior, resulting in situations of serious injury and with serious consequences. That is, the consumption of psychoactive substances, such as alcohol, in adolescence, requires great concern, since this substance causes problems in the organism of the individual who consumes them and also for society.

The media can also be considered responsible for excessive alcohol consumption, since they convey a positive image of the drink, emphasizing that it is a facilitator of social interactions; therefore, there is a need to review the legislation on commercials and advertisements for alcoholic beverages (VARELLA, 2013).

According to Perez and Oliveira (2011) the different treatment given to alcohol should not distract us and lead to consumption beyond appropriate limits. It is conventional to classify those who use alcohol according to the amount ingested within a week. Thus, a light drinker would be someone who consumes from 1 to 100 mL of pure alcohol (volume present in five cans of beer or two shots of whiskey); moderate, from 101 to 300 mL (up to fifteen cans or six shots of whiskey); heavy, for more than 300 mL. But, more broadly, consumption is considered inappropriate when, objectively, it exceeds a predetermined dose or frequency, but also, subjectively, whenever it is used to fill the void of emotions or true social relationships.

Immediate consequences are quite stereotyped in the figure of the drunk. Although the degree of resistance varies from person to person, between 20 and 100mg/dL of alcohol in the blood is enough to cause euphoria and also some loss of motor coordination and cognition; when this concentration exceeds 100 mg/dL, clearly altered behavior, impaired coordination of movements, slurred speech, narrowed consciousness and increased reaction time designate flagrant drunkenness; between 300 and 400 mg/dL, drowsiness already appears, and may progress to coma and death, due to respiratory arrest and drop in blood pressure (PEREZ and OLIVEIRA, 2011).

The consumption of alcoholic beverages is also strongly related to violent behavior and trauma, whether in street fights or domestic violence, which threatens not only physical integrity, but also the integrity of the family structure. Annually, approximately 5.2 million deaths occur worldwide due to accidents and violence; of these, 1.8 million are associated with this habit. Alcoholized people are predisposed to risky sexual behavior, without using condoms,

exposing themselves to STD/AIDS, or unwanted pregnancies; the initiation of other drugs, such as cigarettes and illicit substances, also happens more frequently after alcohol consumption (PEREZ and OLIVEIRA, 2011).

When this use is perpetuated, a state of dependence can arise, which strongly occurs in those individuals with some genetic predisposition, but which is mainly associated with certain consumption patterns, which provide us with some clues. Those who consume alcohol not because they appreciate its flavor, or the drinking ritual, but to get drunk, those who stop going to an event where alcoholic beverages are not served, or even those who frequently drink until they become intoxicated, for example, show that seeks in alcohol - even if to the detriment of its social reason or other pleasures it may provide - its effect as a drug (PEREZ and OLIVEIRA, 2011).

PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATION PROFESSIONALS IN PREVENTING THE USE OF ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES BY ADOLESCENTS

The World Health Organization (WHO) lists alcohol as the most consumed psychoactive substance in the world and as a favorite drug among children and adolescents (VIEIRA, 2007). The National School Health Survey (PeNSE, 2012) interviewed 109,104 students in the 9th grade of elementary school, including 86% aged between 15 and 16 years old, about alcohol use. Contrary to expectations, in this study, girls stood out with 51.7% and boys 48.7%. There are several direct damages caused to students, such as memory loss among young people and lack of attention, triggering learning difficulties and hindering school performance, bringing as a consequence low self-esteem, generating a vicious circle that may lead to an even greater increase in the consumption of alcohol. alcohol.

The family exerts a great influence on adolescents, since it is in the family environment that the adolescent will be characterized, knowing the path he should follow, whether it is correct or not. Hence the importance of establishing educational programs aimed at both adolescents and their parents or guardians, aimed at raising awareness and the necessary clarifications about the harmful effects that excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages can cause (VARELLA, 2013).

The education professional (pedagogue) must have special attention and even training so that he can work with this class and especially with this subject. This happens because this public (adolescents) are people who need a greater degree of attention because they consider themselves insecure, with psycho-emotional suffering and the need to seek out groups in order

to maintain social bonds. For Campos (2003) The bond can be understood as a form of circulation of affection between people. Bonds are built from the moment that some kind of mutual dependency is established: some need help to resolve health issues; others need it to be able to earn a living, practice their profession. That is, for there to be a positive bond, the groups must believe that the team has some power, some ability to solve problems. Therefore, it is up to the education professional to try to get to know his students, becoming familiar with the ways in which they relate to each other. Knowing well the thinking of your students makes the process of interaction between the student and the teacher more accessible, facilitating the communication of better methodological proposals and efficient and effective dynamics. The teacher becomes an interlocutor, who points out, highlights, guides and coordinates.

As Klein (1997, p. 125) states, “it is up to the teacher to place the student in a situation of disequilibrium, that is, of cognitive conflict, for himself, noting the ineffectiveness of his solution, to mobilize in the search for other possibilities.”

The educator must, among other things, identify with what he teaches, get involved in this search and become entangled in the process. And this action must be carried out by trained and qualified professionals, duly qualified, in formal and informal courses. Changes are also needed on the part of schools, in the sense of valuing sex education and health promotion, offering opportunities for guidance and reflection (SOUZA, 2012).

And it is in this gap left by the family system that one infers the essential need for a qualified professional in Human Sciences who, in this case, the education professional (pedagogue) is the most qualified to do so, due to the breadth of his theoretical-humanistic training and his field of action as a technician in human and social sciences where he will develop preventive work linked to the social and cognitive development of adolescents; training for parents with a view to preparing them to face with wisdom and discernment the different stages their children are subject to go through; a technical-scientific training so that teachers can develop the theoretical and methodological contents, referring to the adolescence phase, with more autonomy.

The education professional (pedagogue) will work mainly in partnership with schools, communities and drug use prevention and care programs, with a view to alerting families about the risks inherent in the abusive use of alcoholic beverages by adolescents. This professional can play an important role in promoting the humanistic education of adolescents in various aspects, including the education and training of education professionals aimed at reducing the demand for alcohol and drugs. Understanding that with the changes in paradigms, acting in the

training of other pedagogues and other education professionals, new configurations may occur in the care of different groups in society at the levels of promotion, prevention and social integration, providing the creation of a less stigmatizing view on the teenager and his habits, which many times are not his, but products of a society that imposes as correct and exclusive (CARRARO; RASSOOL; LUIS, 2005).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The use of alcoholic beverages in adolescence has become a problem that worries authorities and technicians in education, health and political management, not only because it has increased dramatically in recent times, but also because it is a habit that is stimulated and reinforced by society in general. This problem is directly linked to the feeling of power that drinking causes in the individual, making him feel braver, bolder and happier, as it reduces anxiety and stress levels, causing significant increases in *adrenaline*, which, for young people, helps to combat shyness. Unfortunately, on the other hand, there has been an increase in violence, aggression, fights, high-speed car races and an increase in the number of accidents involving pedestrians and drivers. There are also non-consensual carnal unions arising from the state of numbness that affects adolescents, resulting in forced defloration, unwanted pregnancies and transmission of infectious and contagious diseases, among many others.

Even though teenagers appear to be physically developed, their brains continue to develop and mature, especially in the frontal regions that are associated with high levels of thinking. In fact, excessive alcohol use can disrupt the growth of normal brain cells, which can interfere with teens' performance in school and sports. There is also the feeling of overcoming obstacles placed by society as barriers that the teenager is forced to overcome and who, without being able to count on the support of family members, rely on alcohol and the results are the sad fatalities that are commonly witnessed.

It should be noted that the consumption of alcoholic beverages by adolescents does not mean, under any circumstances, that they will become alcoholics in adult life. It is necessary to be careful and try to work on their self-esteem so that this addiction does not become an outlet for their socio-family frustrations and becomes a lifeline for coping with adult life.

In the meantime, the education professional (pedagogue) assumes a relevant role, given his technical-humanistic qualifications and capacity for social entrepreneurship, which, together with the Family Health Strategies posts, schools, communities and families can

contribute severely to that the consumption of alcoholic beverages by adolescents will not become an endemic problem.

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